

small shrub growing abundantly in central and eastern provinces of India. A perusal of literature revealed that some works⁴ have been reported on this plant. We now report the results of our systematic screening of the leaves of this plant.

The air-dried powdered leaves of *P. tithymaloides* were successively extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene. The petroleum ether extract was concentrated and chromatographed over silica gel. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) afforded a solid, m.p. 88°; $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3360 cm^{-1} , identified as n-hentriacontanol by the usual comparison (m m.p., co-tlc and co-ir).

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and benzene (1:1) mixture furnished a solid crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–methanol (3:1), $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}$ (M^+ 428) m.p. 132–35°, which gave yellow colour with tetranitromethane. Ir spectrum of the compound showed ion bands at $\nu_{\max}$ (KBr) 3420 (hydroxyl) and 1640 cm^{-1} (unsaturation), and formed an amorphous monoacetate $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_2$ on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine. The ¹H nmr spectrum (90 MHz; CDCl_3) of the compound recorded peaks at δ 0.75 (15H, s) for five tertiary C-methyls, a doublet at δ 1.15 (3H, d, *J* 6 Hz) for one secondary C-methyl, a singlet at δ 1.65 (6H, s) for a =C(CH₃)₂ and a broad multiplet around δ 5.65 (1H, m) for an olefinic unsaturation, thus indicating it to be a tetracyclic triterpene. The acetyl derivative of the parent compound on catalytic hydrogenation in glacial acetic acid with Adams catalyst afforded dammaranyl acetate⁵, $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{56}\text{O}_2$, m.p. 138–40°, which on hydrolysis with 10% ethanolic KOH furnished a compound, $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}$ (M^+ 430), m.p. 125–26° identified as demmaranol-A⁵ by m m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with the authentic sample, and conclusively establishing thereby that the triterpene is dehydroadammaranol-A, the location of the olefinic unsaturation at C₂₃–C₂₄ being ascertained from the formation of acetone characterised as its dinitrophenylhydrazone during ozonolysis of the acetate of the triterpene. Incidentally it is the first isolation of this triterpene from plant origin.

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Hydrodynamic Determination of Size and Shapes of Near Spherical Macromolecules

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THE equation,

$$V_E = \frac{[(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 1]}{C[1.35(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 0.1]} \quad (1)$$

was proposed¹ after the rearrangement of Eiler equation^{2,3} for the determination of voluminosities (V_E) of casein micelles in moderately dilute solutions. The η_{rel} and C were relative viscosity and concentration (g ml^{-1}) respectively. Equation (1) was modified in these laboratories⁴ to

$$V_E = \lim_{C \rightarrow 0} \frac{[(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 1]}{C[1.35(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 0.1]} \quad (2)$$

and the linear plot of

$$\{(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 1\} \{C[1.35(\eta_{rel})^{0.5} - 0.1]\}^{-1} \text{ vs } C \quad (3)$$

extrapolated to zero concentration gave the value of voluminosities of salt-soluble mungbean proteins in very dilute solutions.

Simha⁵ equation,

$$[\eta] = \nu V_E \quad (4)$$

where, $[\eta]$ is intrinsic viscosity and ν is Simha shape factor, provides an easy hydrodynamic approach to the determination of molecular parameters of macromolecules, if V_E is known.

In this test study the molecular parameters such as voluminosities, viscosities, Simha shape factors, frictional coefficient ratios of the bovine serum albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin were hydrodynamically determined and which compared well with the literature values obtained from more sophisticated methods.

Experimental

Pure bovine serum albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin (Sigma) were used. All reagents used were of A.R. grade. All-glass double-distilled water was used. Present studies were carried out at $40.0 \pm 0.1^\circ$. All letter representations in different equations express the same quantity.

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Partial specific volumes ($\bar{v}_o$) were pycnometrically determined⁶, using equation (5),

$$\bar{v}_o = (1/d_o) (1 - \Delta d/C) \quad (5)$$

Plot of $(1/d_o) (1 - \Delta d/C)$ vs C extrapolated to zero concentration, gave the value of $\bar{v}_o$, where d_o is density of the solvent (g ml^{-1}), d the density of solution (g ml^{-1}), $\Delta d = d - d_o$, and C the concentration of protein (g ml^{-1}). Protein content (C) of the solution was estimated gravimetrically by initially keeping the proteins at 60° overnight followed by drying at 100° to constant weight,

Intrinsic $[\eta]$, kinematic $[\eta/d]$ and relative viscosities (η_{rel}) were determined using multigradient Ubbelohde viscometer^{7,8}. Tanford⁹ equation,

$$[\eta] = [\eta/d] + \frac{1}{d_o} (1 - \bar{v}_o d_o) \quad (6)$$

was used to calculate $\bar{v}_o$. The plots of equation (3) were found to be hyperbolic. Value of V_E was obtained using Lagrange's equation¹⁰. Simha equation⁵ (4) was used for computing ν . The equation¹¹,

$$f/f_o = F \left(\frac{V_E}{\bar{v}_o} \right)^{1/3} \quad (7)$$

was used to calculate the frictional coefficient ratio f/f_o and F is a function of axial ratio¹². Axial ratios (a/b) were calculated¹³ from the value of F .

Results and Discussion

The various respective experimental parameters (40°) of albumin, hemoglobin and egg albumin are presented in Table I. With the decrease in concentration of protein in solution, the values of partial

specific volumes increased and viscosities decreased. The slope for the determination of partial specific volumes and intrinsic and kinematic viscosities of the experimental proteins indicated the extensive solute-solute interactions in the solutions of sample proteins. The experimental and reported (Table I) values of different parameters are in agreement. This approach is unique because of simplicity and rapidity of experimentation. It enables the determination of size and shapes of near-spherical macromolecules in solutions under different physiological conditions.

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TABLE I—LITERATURE AND EXPERIMENTAL PARAMETERS

Parameter	Proteins (mol. wt.)		
	Bovine serum albumin (89000)	Hemoglobin (64500)	Egg albumin (45000)
$\bar{v}_o$ (ml g^{-1}) ^a	0.712	0.757	0.725
$\bar{v}_o$ (ml g^{-1}) ^{b,1}	0.708	0.758	0.718
$[\eta]$ (ml g^{-1}) ^a	4.0	3.5	3.4
$[\eta]$ (ml g^{-1}) ²	3.7 ^a	3.6 ^b	4.0 ¹
$[\eta/d]$ (ml g^{-1}) ^a	3.7	3.25	3.15
V_E (ml g^{-1}) ^a	1.26	1.05	0.79
V_E (ml g^{-1}) ^{b,2}	1.12	1.09	0.85
ν^a	3.25	3.86	4.81
$\nu^{b,2}$	3.80	3.80	4.66
(from axial ratios)			
$f/f_o^{b,2}$	1.31	1.22	1.23
(from diffusion coeff.)			
$f/f_o^{b,2}$	1.33	1.28	1.19
(from sedimentation coeff.)			
$f/f_o^{b,1}$	1.36	1.26	1.24
a/b^a	2.4	2.6	3.9
$a/b^{b,2}$	2.5	2.5	4.0

^a Experimental value. ^b Calculated value. ² Literature value.

¹Ref. 9. ²Ref. 11. ³ $f/f_o = F(V_E/\bar{v}_o)^{1/3}$. ⁴Ref. 15. ⁵Ref. 13. ⁶Ref. 14.

Complex Formation with some Bidentate Ligands. Part-V. Thermodynamic Aspects of Complexation Reactions of some Bivalent Metal Ions with *vic*-Hydroxyaldehyde Thiosemicarbazones

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SALICYLALDEHYDE thiosemicarbazone (SATSC), 5-nitrosalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (5-NSATSC) and 4-methylsalicylaldehyde thiosemicarbazone (4-MSATSC) form chelates with many metals. The present paper aims at measuring the thermodynamic formation constants of the chelates of Co^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Mg^{II} with the above ligands using Calvin-Bjerrum pH-titration technique